

Corticospinal and corticoreticulospinal projections have discrete but complementary roles in chronic motor behaviors after stroke

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A) Accuracy

B) Path Irregularity

Supplemental Figure 1. Motor deficits in stroke compared to healthy subjects. Single dots represent individual subjects. The box plot displays the median (horizontal white line) and the interquartile range (IQR) between the first and third quartile. The whiskers show values within 1.5*IQR. **A) Accuracy.** Stroke subjects had higher error rates than healthy subjects in both muscles (BIC, $p = 0.003$; FDI, $p = 0.002$). Error rate was comparable between muscles within subject group. **B) Path irregularity.** Stroke subjects had greater path irregularity than healthy subjects in both UE muscles (BIC, $p < 0.0001$; FDI, $p = 0.003$). Path irregularity was comparable between muscles within subject group. * $p < 0.05$